

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-IMPROVEMENT OF FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8394563>

Zaylobidinova.D.G

Fergana State University base doktorant

Annotation

This article is devoted to the topic of socio-psychological aspects of educating future foreign language teachers. Also, in the text of the article, issues such as psychological foundations, social psychological determinants, professional motives formed in teachers, tolerance and empathic abilities are widely covered.

Key words

Teacher, education, pedagogical activity, professional, work on oneself, tolerance, empathic ability, success motives, knowledge, competence, profession, self-development.

The main problem of the present time is the theoretical, practical, methodological approach to the professional training of future Foreign Language teachers and the improvement of the conditions and its methodologies for special training, the identification of such as professional knowledge, skills and qualifications, the ability to work independently, which will be necessary for the success of future Foreign Language teachers. Therefore, it is of scientific importance to identify and evaluate the socio-psychological aspects of the upbringing of work on oneself specific to successful, creative teachers, to modernize the system of psychological knowledge, integrate it into the requirements of society, as well as to introduce new psychodiagnostic methodologies aimed at researching the psychological conditions for the upbringing of the ability to work on oneself, to, it assumes the development of advanced innovative mechanisms. Also, in the work of research on the socio-psychological aspects of the upbringing of work on oneself, it is necessary first of all to increase the role of advanced psychodiagnostic methodologies and questionnaires, to modernize methodological support for the problem, to introduce local methodologies and personality surveys based on new innovative approaches, and to raise it to a new level of quality. In order for a teacher to be self-educated, he must first thoroughly study himself in detail, be able to see the achievements and shortcomings of his work. It is necessary for self-study and understanding of another person. It is impossible to study oneself as a

person without studying other achievements and comparing oneself with others. The property of self-awareness, self-assessment is formed in the process of relations with other people, during joint activities. The pedagogical task is to help the student who seeks to educate his will on his own, in addition to showing only the range of volitional qualities, revealing their inner connection with important moral Principles, showing what methods of developing volitional qualities are less effective and which do not help seriously. First of all, the teacher must learn what are the qualities of pedagogical ability in himself. An outstanding teacher of pedagogical activity is sincerely devoted to work, what shortcomings Hech does not suffer. A teacher who loves his profession is constantly working diligently on increasing his ideological-political level and expanding his circle of knowledge, on deep knowledge of his subject. It is known that humanity has so many opportunities for maturation that it is necessary to set historical self-education as an honorable task for itself that it can be achieved by working on itself with patience in the pursuit of the goals of achieving them. According to scholars, "the educator must shape the ideal of humanity in himself" was brought to hulusa. It is the formation of the beautiful qualities of humanity in itself that forms the foundation of the professional skill of each educator. On this foundation, the professional skills of an educator can grow day by day thanks to work on themselves. Self-discipline encourages initiative and independence. Teaches to analyze his personal qualities, to think about his actions. For self-control, it monitors its own behavior, discipline, increasing positive habits and, on the contrary, decreasing negative habits. Self-assessment helps the teacher, in assessing their potential, to achieve self-satisfaction. Together with self-education, the teacher works tirelessly on himself, constantly cultivating his ideological-political consciousness and improving his pedagogical skills. An advanced teacher seeks to know the innovations in pedagogy all the time, tries to use the experiences of other teachers and use his own personal experiences, as well as summarize his personal experiences. If a person is sought, works on his abilities, matures good qualities in himself, his reputation, position will also rise to this level and will always be in the eyes of el. The teacher must educate in himself the observant, the caring. It is one of the prerequisites for the teacher to acquire independent knowledge and improve his qualifications. Eastern thinkers rightly said that a teacher can be a teacher if he or she reads it, and that if he or she stops reading, then teaching will also fade. The motivation of future teachers for professional self-improvement is a set of all motives and conditions that determine, direct and regulate the process of professional self-improvement of specialists. Hence, the system of relations of future teachers, which

determines the motivation for professional self-development, includes three criteria: 1) the attitude of the individual to his professional activities; 2) his attitude to himself as a specialist; 3) his attitude to self-improvement in the professional sphere. An analysis of the problem, theoretical considerations confirm that the future successful activities of future Foreign Language teachers are hampered by the following factors: ignorance of the psychological mechanisms of self-realization; ignorance of the content, structure and logic of the process of professional self-improvement; lack of knowledge of the main methods and methods of self-development; psychological unpreparedness for Education, fear of; Lack of experience in solving specific tasks of personal self-development. Another important condition for eliminating the above factors is to stimulate the activities of teachers. Because, in studies, it has been proven that a person who does not react to his work loses interest in him over time. There are two ways to further enhance the performance of work on oneself-positive (reward) and negative (punishment).

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of active methods in higher education, being a prerequisite for the training of highly qualified specialists, leads to positive many results. At the same time, such conditions make it widely possible to form knowledge, skills and qualifications by involving future Foreign Language teachers in active educational and cognitive activities. In the end, all information about the field becomes the personal knowledge of the students.

REFERENCES:

1. Abdusmatova Sh.S. Burkhanova M.B. (2020). Features of the relationship of parents with many children in the family. *Oriental Art and Culture*
2. Goziev E.G'. Higher School Psychology. – T.: The reader, 1997. – 197 b. B.Kadyrov” psychological aspects of preparation for the choice of profession and professional diagnosis « Tashkent, 2001. – 36 b.
3. Baydzhанov, B. X. (2020). Mechanisms for the effective application of advanced foreign experiments in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 1(2), 514-519.
4. Baydzhанov, B. K. (2021). PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (7), 171-178.
5. Baydzhанov, B. K. (2022). Methodology of Pedagogical Science and its Axiological Possibilities. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 352-363.

6. Baydzhhanov, B. (2021, March). COMPATIBILITY OF NEW
7. Dilshodovich, I. S. (2022). AS AN EXCELLENT BASIS FOR THE FORMATION OF FAMILIAL COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS. JOURNAL OF INTERDISCIPLINARY INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(12), 1210-1215.
8. Dilshodovich, I. S. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILISTIC COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS. JOURNAL OF INTERDISCIPLINARY INNOVATION AND SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 2(18), 874-879.
9. Dilshodovich, I. S. (2022). THE USE OF NATIONAL CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS IN PREPARING STUDENTS FOR FAMILY LIFE. CREATIVE TEACHER, 2 (23), 476-479.
10. Dilshodovich, I. S. (2022). OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR FAMILY LIFE CONTENT AND LEPROSY. *Novosti obrazovania: issledovanie V XXI Veke*, 1(2), 117-123.
11. Dilshodovich, I. S. (2023). DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF FORMATION OF FAMILIAL COMPETENCE IN ADOLESCENT BOYS. *European journal of education and applied psychology*, (1), 3-6.